

A Note on the Influence of Acidity of Agar on the Liesegang Rings of Lead Chromate and Lead Iodide.

BY H. M. MAPARA.

It is well known that good rings of lead chromate are obtained in some samples of agar, while in others they are not observed at all. With traces of acetic acid, the rings are somewhat well defined and slightly further apart (Hatscheck, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1921, **A 99**, 496). Results on the influence of the degree of acidity of agar on the Liesegang rings of lead chromate and lead iodide are given in this paper (*cf.* Desai and Nabar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, **9**, 141; Desai and Naik, *ibid.*, 1934, **11**, 69).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Rings of lead chromate in agar.—Chemically pure agar powder (8.9 g.) soaked in distilled water (200 c.c.) for 24 hours was heated on a water-bath for nearly 1½ hours, and loss of water during heating being made good by addition of fresh, distilled water. In thoroughly cleaned and dried test tubes of the same internal diameter, 12 c.c. of agar, 4.0 c.c. of a 0.5% lead acetate and suitable amounts of acetic acid or sodium acetate were added. The p_H of the agar solution thus varied from 2.4 to 9.25, p_H of original agar being 5.94 (colorimetric). The total volume was made the same (20 c.c.) with distilled water, the contents of each test tube were stirred and allowed to stand for 24 hours to set to a gel. 3 C.c. of a 1% solution of potassium chromate were allowed to diffuse at the top of the gel in each test tube. The changes in the test tubes were frequently noted each day until potassium chromate had diffused right upto the bottom of the test tube. Only normal bands were obtained, the anomalous bands (Hatscheck, *loc. cit.*) being absent due to the test tubes having not been exposed to light. The distances between successive rings were measured by

means of a cathetometer. The following is the summary of observations:

(i) No well defined rings were obtained in samples of agar having a p_H range from 2.4 to 2.96, as well as those having p_H higher than about 9.25. Samples of agar of p_H 3.08 to 9.02 gave well defined rings.

(ii) The time for the appearance of the first ring increases with an increase of the p_H of the gel.

(iii) The distance between the successive rings increases with all samples of agar.

(iv) The thickness of the ring in any one sample of the gel increases from the first ring to the last ring, but its compactness decreases at the same time.

(v) The distance between successive rings decreases with an increase of p_H , the number of rings increasing at the same time.

(vi) The thickness of the rings decreases with an increase of p_H of agar.

(vii) The size of particles in the rings increases with an increase of p_H upto 8.04, the particles being again smaller in samples of gel having p_H higher than this value.

Rings of lead iodide in agar.—The details of the experiments were exactly the same as in the case of rings of lead chromate except that in this case, the gel was impregnated with 2 c.c. of a 40% solution of potassium iodide and 3.0 c.c. of a 30% solution of lead nitrate were added at the top for diffusion after setting of the gel. The total volume in this case was also made to 20 c.c. by adding suitable amounts of distilled water. The following is the summary of the results:

(i) The time for the appearance of the first ring generally increases with an increase of the p_H of the gel.

(ii) Good well-defined rings are obtained in samples of agar having a p_H range from 2.40 to 5.94; broken rings are obtained in samples of gel of p_H higher than 6.

(iii) The distance between successive rings in any sample of gel increases from the first ring to the last ring, but its compactness decreases at the same time.

(iv) The distance between the successive rings decreases with an increase of p_H , the number of rings increasing at the same time upto p_H value of about 8.

(v) The thickness of rings decreases with an increase of p_H of agar.

(vi) The size of particles in the rings increases with an increase of p_H of the sample of the gel.

The results show that there is a definite range of p_H of the agar gel within which good rings of lead chromate and lead iodide can be obtained.

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
WILSON COLLEGE, BOMBAY 7.

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Hydrazinates of Metallic Thiosulphates.

BY PRIYADARANJAN RÂY AND ANIL KUMAR MAZUMDAR.

Several investigators (Curtius and Schrader, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1894, ii, 50, 311; Hofmann and Marburg, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 2019; Franzen and Mayer, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1909, 50, 247; Franzen and Lueking, *ibid.*, 1911, 70, 145) have shown that hydrazine combines with many metallic salts, especially with those of the transitional elements, to form complex compounds similar to those given by ammonia and ethylenediamine. This tendency to complex-formation with hydrazine is pronounced even in the case of unstable and insoluble salts, as illustrated by the formation of hydrazinates of sulphites and nitrites of Mn, Co, Ni, Zn, and Cd (Rây and Goswami, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, 168, 329) and of the corresponding thiocyanates (Rây and Sarkar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 321). In all these cases the prominent type is tetra-co-ordinated, with one or two exceptions, assuming that the hydrazine molecule acts as a bidentate group like ethylenediamine, e.g. $-\text{NH}_2'-\text{NH}_2-$. With nickel sulphite only, it exhibits a co-ordination number of six, with cadmium sulphite it falls down to two, with cobalt nitrite it is three (*cf.* Rây and Goswami, *loc. cit.*).

In the case of salts with anions of stronger acids, formation of both hexa- and tetra-co-ordination has been observed, and it is generally assumed that the highest or limit co-ordination number is more frequently exhibited by the metals in their salts with stronger acids,